

THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE OF TOUGH COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The delamination behaviour of AS4/PEEK is characterized over a range of temperatures, from -30°C to 120°C . Double Cantilever Beam and End Notch Flexure specimens have allowed both mode I and mode II loading to be studied. Results are compared with those obtained for two carbon/epoxy systems, T300/914 and IM6/6376, under similar conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The dramatic increase in the use of composite materials in recent years has been accompanied by significant material developments. Particular attention has been directed towards toughness, in order to improve resistance to delamination, a very common failure mode in first generation carbon/epoxy composites. Two principal approaches may be distinguished; toughening of existing tri- and tetra-functional epoxy based systems and adoption of intrinsically tougher thermoplastic matrices. The former approach includes the use of flexibilizers and interleaf layers (1,2). Examples of the latter are PEEK, PPS, and thermoplastic polyimides (3-5).

In evaluating the delamination behaviour of composite materials the use of a fracture mechanics approach has proved effective (6,7). Its application to thermoset and thermoplastic composites has enabled toughness improvements to be quantified under mode I (opening) and mode II (shear) loading. Thus mode I values of G_{IC} in excess of 2 kJ/m^2 have been obtained for some thermoplastics (3), compared with values around 150 J/m^2 for early C/epoxy systems. Mode II value improvements have generally been more modest; a number of mechanisms combine to resist the initiation and propagation of a delamination and requirements for high values of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} are not identical, as will be discussed later.

A certain amount of data characterizing the behaviour of toughened composites is therefore already available. This data has generally been obtained from tests on relatively thin (3 to 5 mm) double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens at room temperature, at loading rates of 1-5 mm/min. However composite structures in service may undergo considerable temperature variations and be loaded at rates ranging from creep to impact conditions. It is thus of practical importance to know the response of toughened composites when these parameters are varied, particularly as the properties of their matrix materials might be expected to be more viscoelastic in nature than the early epoxy matrices.

Berglund (8) and Smiley (9) have examined the effect of loading rate on the delamination behaviour of C/PEEK, the latter noting a pronounced drop in resistance at high rates. To date however little work has been published on the effect of temperature on delamination behaviour apart from the work of Russell & Street (7,10) and Garg (11), on relatively brittle C/epoxy materials. It is the aim of the present paper to describe results from a series of tests in which temperature was varied over a range from -30 °C to +120°C. A fracture mechanics approach was applied to tests on C/PEEK and C/epoxy under mode I and mode II loading and the effect of temperature on delamination mechanisms is discussed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Three composite materials were studied;

a) AS4/PEEK, polyetheretherketone reinforced by 61% vol. AS4 fibres (APC2), supplied by ICI plc, Wilton, UK, in the form of 5.2 and 20 mm thick panels.

b) IM6/6376, a flexibilized epoxy reinforced by 61% vol. intermediate modulus fibres, produced by Ciba Geigy. Panels 4mm thick were produced from prepreg following manufacturers curing schedule (175 °C for 2 hours).

c) T300/914, a relatively low toughness carbon/epoxy supplied by Ciba Geigy, Duxford, UK, in the form of 5mm thick panels, 60% vol. fibres, postcured at 190°C for 4 hours .

All panels were unidirectional and contained mid-plane starter cracks.

Methods

-Transverse tensile tests were performed on coupons (130mmx10mmx5mm) cut from the same panels as the DCB specimens. Loading rate and test temperature were varied.

-Mode I tests were performed on DCB specimens of 2 thicknesses as shown in Figure 1. The loading rate was 2 mm/min, unless otherwise specified. A temperature chamber enabled temperatures from -30 °C to +120°C to be obtained. A dummy specimen containing a thermocouple was used to check temperature equilibrium before and during each test. At least 4 specimens were tested at each temperature.

Data reduction methods were of 2 types, as detailed elsewhere (12); the areas method, involving load/unload cycles, and a compliance calibration

based on Berry's method using specimens with different initial crack lengths.

-Mode II tests were performed on End Notch Flexure (ENF) specimens (7) of dimensions as shown in Figure 1. Specimens were precracked a few mm in mode I. Loading rate was 0.5 mm/min. for all tests. The shear-corrected beam theory expression was employed with the maximum load (13) to determine G_{IIC} but other data reduction methods are discussed later.

Figure 1. Specimen dimensions for (a) thin and (b) thick DCB specimens and (c) ENF specimen. Dimensions in mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Transverse Tensile tests

Before examining the delamination behaviour of the materials, a series of transverse tensile tests was performed on AS4/PEEK. This enabled the influence of temperature and loading rate on matrix and interface to be studied. The tensile strength results are shown in Figure 2, together with examples of the two types of fracture surface obtained.

As might be expected increasing temperature leads to an increase in failure strain and reduced tensile strength, accompanied by the appearance of considerable matrix deformation as its glass transition temperature (145 °C) is approached. Little rate sensitivity is noted until temperatures above 80 °C. Good fibre-matrix adhesion was observed for all loading conditions.

Figure 2. Results from Transverse Tensile tests, and fracture surfaces; $20 \mu\text{m}$
 a) 25 °C , 2mm/min. b) 120 °C , 2mm/min.

Mode I delamination behaviour

The mode I delamination behaviour of the 3 materials is summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1
 Results from DCB tests, mean (S.D.) values, kJ/m^2 loading rate 2mm/min.

MATERIAL	t (mm)	25 °C		-30 °C	120 °C
		G_{IC} Init.	G_{IP} (Stable)	G_{IP} Stable	Propagation
AS4/PEEK	5	1.46(.09)	2.40(.14)	Unstable	3.93(.18)
AS4/PEEK	20	1.5 to 3.5	Unstable	Unstable	4.43(.36)
T300/914	5	0.18(.01)	0.18(.01)	0.17(.02)	0.26(.02)
IM6/6376	4	0.18(.02)	0.63(.04)	---	---

All values in this table were determined using the compliance method. Initiation values were defined by acoustic emission and were quite reproducible, except in the case of thick AS4/PEEK specimens. For these specimens G_{IC} values were highly dependent on starter crack length, elevated values being caused by the rate sensitivity of a resin-rich region in front of the aluminium foil starter crack. Subsequent propagation in these specimens at room temperature and -30 °C was highly

Figure 3. (a) Stable Propagation ; G_{IP} values, Areas method, Mean \pm S.D. AS4/PEEK (2mm/min) fracture surface. % stable propagation, Mean \pm Max, Min values, measured from Thin, 5mm. (b) Unstable propagation values; compliance method, Mean \pm S.D. at onset of instability and at arrest.

unstable so values are not presented here. At 120°C similar stable propagation values are obtained for both AS4/PEEK specimen thicknesses.

For T300/914, room temperature initiation and propagation values were very similar and no fibre bridging was observed. G_{IP} values increased significantly as temperature was raised from 25°C to 120°C.

For IM6/6376 extensive fibre bridging raised the 25°C propagation value. Establishment of an equilibrium zone of bridging fibres resulted in a reproducible propagation value. Mode I test temperature was not varied for this material.

While the C/epoxies may be characterized by initiation and propagation values, to fully assess influence of temperature on the AS4/PEEK more information is required. Zones of both stable and unstable propagation are observed and Figure 3 gives a complete description of the behaviour of the thin specimens.

In Figure 3a a large increase in both the amount of stable propagation and the corresponding G_{IP} value is revealed as temperature is raised. The distinction between stable and unstable fracture surfaces has been shown elsewhere (14); here the effect of temperature on the stable propagation zones is shown in Figure 4. The increased ability of the PEEK matrix to flow at elevated temperatures, and in particular extensive drawing, are clearly shown. A number of fibrils are drawn to over 100% and matrix drawing is the main energy dissipation mechanism responsible for the dramatic increase in G_{IP} .

Figure 4. DCB fracture surfaces, thin specimens, stable propagation
a) -30°C b) 120°C

There are several possible explanations for the appearance of unstable zones of propagation during tests on DCB specimens (which are often chosen because this geometry encourages stability). Some epoxy formulations exhibit a similar behaviour, and crack tip blunting has been proposed as a possible explanation (15). The temperature dependence of yield stress, and consequent ease of plastic deformation at higher temperature (or slower loading rate) might be invoked to explain the viscoelastic nature of the phenomenon.

It is clear from the transverse tensile tests and from published work (16) that PEEK is quite sensitive to temperature and rate parameters in this range, but the seemingly random distribution of stable and unstable zones must also be related to the irregularity of the crack path (17) and the fibre bridges which result. It seems unlikely that the

breakage of fibres alone initiates unstable propagation; thick specimens, too rigid to allow sufficient opening for fibre breakage, are extremely unstable and it is therefore high crack tip strain rate which is the determining factor. In thinner specimens however, fibre bundle breakage may contribute to locally raising strain rate.

Mode II delamination behaviour

Mode II testing of the two C/epoxies results in unambiguous values of G_{IIC} as virtually linear load-displacement plots are obtained up to unstable propagation, at all temperatures. The maximum load is therefore used to determine G_{IIC} , shown as a function of temperature in Figure 5.

For AS4/PEEK however, some stable propagation occurs before the maximum load at all temperatures studied here. After the peak load is reached propagation may be stable or unstable according to test temperature, stability increasing as temperature is increased. The problem of sub-critical crack growth has been discussed by Carlsson et al.(18) and a calculation based on non-linear fracture mechanics has been proposed. The G_{IIC} values for AS4/PEEK shown in Figure 5 were calculated using the maximum load. A non-linear calculation was also carried out and this resulted in higher G_{IIC} values, but the trend shown here was unaffected; as temperature is increased G_{IIC} decreases slightly. The drop in G_{IIC} observed by other authors, corresponding to a transition to completely unstable propagation at high loading rates (9), was not observed. The 2 types of fracture surface are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Influence of temperature on mode II delamination, ENF.
AS4/PEEK ; Mean \pm Max, Min values. C/epoxies ; Mean only, scatter < 50 J/m².

Figure 6. Mode II fracture surfaces, a) stable , b) unstable

The influence of temperature on mode II delamination resistance is very different to that found under mode I loading; the G_{IIC} values of the C/epoxy systems are insensitive to temperature over the range studied and no differences are observed on fracture surfaces as temperature is increased. Garg suggests that the interface is critical under shear loading (11) and the IM6/6376 fracture surfaces revealed more interface failure than those of T300/914. This may be due to a more resistant matrix, or to differences in bonding to the (smaller) IM6 fibre.

Apart from differences related to stability of propagation, mode II AS4/PEEK fracture surfaces varied little with temperature; in stable propagation considerable matrix ductility is apparent at all temperatures, whereas unstable failure occurs close to the interface but rarely leaves clean fibres. The "hackle" features seen on the epoxy fracture surfaces are not observed in AS4/PEEK. Given that enhanced matrix ductility at higher temperature is not reflected in higher mode II fracture energies for this composite, the interface region is presumably playing a more important role; Russell has proposed an interfacial energy reduction to explain mode II temperature dependence in carbon/epoxy (19).

The slight decrease in G_{IIC} values for AS4/PEEK, when compared to the net increase in G_{Ip} as temperature is increased, suggests that at a certain temperature pure mode I will no longer be the lowest energy failure mode; the exact temperature will depend on the data reduction methods employed, but this observation underlines the importance of the development of reliable shear and mixed mode delamination tests to complement the DCB test.

Temperature-loading rate superposition

It has been shown elsewhere that certain composite properties such as transverse tensile strength may be treated using a time-temperature superposition (20). In addition, the work of Bitner et al (21) showed that such an approach could be applied to the fracture of pure epoxy resins and this naturally leads to speculation on whether the delamination of composite materials might also be amenable to this type of interpretation.

A great deal of data would be required to completely resolve this question but some comments may be made.

Mode I delamination of AS4/PEEK involves two parameters which increase with temperature ; the amount of stable propagation and the critical strain energy release rate for this propagation. An approximation of the former was plotted in Figure 3a and in a previous paper the rate dependence of this parameter at room temperature was presented (14) ; from these data a temperature drop from 25°C to -30°C corresponds to a loading rate increase from 2 to 200 mm/min.

However this is a rather simplistic approach and in considering the G_{IP} values a weighted shift factor is required, related to $(T-T_g)$, as a significant rise is only noted when the temperature approaches the glass transition temperature of the PEEK (145°C). Such a factor might be obtained from dynamic mechanical analysis as shown in previous work (19) or from the transverse tensile tests over a similar range of conditions, Figure 2. In published results (9,22) over a range of loading rates no increase in G_{IP} values was measured even at rates as low as 0.25 mm/min. ; very slow tests would therefore be required to verify the validity of a superposition theory.

CONCLUSIONS

Mode I delamination resistance of both tough and relatively brittle composites increases as temperature is increased.

Mode II delamination behaviour is far less sensitive to temperature change.

As temperature is raised mode I loading will cease to be the lowest energy failure mode for AS4/PEEK.

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